

SOCIAL MEDIA ETHICS AMONG ADOLESCENTS

KRISTINA NURHAYATI

Communication Studies Post Graduate Program Sahid University of Jakarta

xtinlara@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

As one of the country's largest mobile phone and internet users, Indonesian have a variety of interesting complexity of the problems to be studied. Among them is the use of social media among adolescents. Social media, on the one hand, provide a variety of benefits to its users while on the other hand can also be detrimental. In the last few years, social media use among children and adolescents in the media of concern related to the period of negative things that arise as a result of the use of social media like Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, Line, WeChat, etc. As a developing country with a population of teens who reach 30 percent of the total population of the adolescent, problems and the use of social media need attention. Additionally crucial role for parents in facing various problems faced by teenagers. This study aims to find out about any knowledge possessed by the parents about the social media used by teenagers as well as various activities undertaken by parents associated with social media used by teenagers. The concept used in this study is the concept of the characteristics of the media, the concept of family and youth. The method used is descriptive qualitative data collection through survey interviews with some parents who have teenagers of social media users. The results showed that in general parents are aware of the type of social media use of children, time spent using social media, teens touch with anyone in social media, what is talked about in social media. Parents are also members of adolescent friendships in social media as a control function although teens generally do not want it.

Keywords: Ethics, Social Media, Youth.

INTRODUCTION

Born in the digital age of today Indonesian teens so synonymous with a smartphone in the hands of nearly 24 hours. They are preoccupied with the online world, from social media such as Facebook, Twitter, IG, Youtube, to instant messaging such as Line,

Whatsapp, WeChat, etc. Internet usage among teens is not a stranger. Internet is a new communications technology that allows users to obtain information on Internet usage is considered more practical and efficient. The world of education is one of the areas that use the Internet for the benefit of

improving the quality of an educational institution. Education is the holder of an important role in the progress of a nation, for the world of education is to print the next generation. The Internet can be regarded as a virtual library that stores a variety of knowledge in it. The Internet can be used as an alternative source of knowledge.

Social media use among teenagers start worrying, many problems begin to emerge. Activity greatly affects the virtual world in real life. Misunderstandings often occur in the association. Even crimes act often occur due to this misunderstanding. The authors found social media ethics should be developed even have to go inside one of the subjects in school.

Research Limitation

Many problems and misunderstandings that have arisen, the authors limit the issues on good social media ethics among adolescents.

Research Problem

Should social media ethics among adolescents?

Research purposes

To determine the need for social media ethics among adolescents

The benefits of research

a. For educators

To be able to add additional material in teaching ethics in schools

b. For parents

Adding more information as to why need to provide supervision when adolescents socially mediated.

Literature Review

Research conducted by Bhrata Kusuma 2004 from the Master of Science in Communication Studies Post Graduate Program of the Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, University of Indonesia (2004), entitled "Comparison of Communications Virtual Worlds and the Real World" (A Study Library). The qualitative research which took place in Jakarta found that the formation of a group mailing lists are generally preceded by common interests among some participants or it could be at the initiative of a person who then invited participants from mailing lists or an email database collected. The formation of the group mailing lists as common interests, the grouping that occurs in the online community is based on their interests. No difference in the online community group characteristics in principle based on the number of members in a group or by other aspects. Communications were established among fellow members in a group solely based on the context in the absence of nonverbal communication in media. Communication in a group mailing list often feels dry and could trigger errors in judgment on the personality of its online partners. Although the group of cyberspace is not a cohesive group, for certain matters

concerning the interests or feelings of the people, groups of the virtual world can become radicalized.

Critics of the results of this study, according to the author, should be studied more deeply about what caused the characteristics of virtual groups and real-world groups have in common. The use of the theory that made, using only analysis of group dynamics theory, the theory of symbolic interaction should also be used to analyze the symbols and meanings exchanges occurring within the mailing list.

The definition of Internet

In the use of the Internet, teens ranked first. The Internet has become part of their lifestyle. Almost every activity of adolescents is influenced by the Internet, ranging from the use of social networks to their education.

Definition of Computer-Mediated Communication

As we know that Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC) is a term used to perform communication between two or more people who can benefit interact through a computer. What is meant here is not how two or more machines can interact, but how two or more people can communicate with each other using computer aids through the existing

application program on the computer. With this in mind, that which is required of participants in carrying out communication with the CMC the communicant must involve two components, namely computer and internet networks. Not just a computer and Internet networks, but on the computer, there should be a specific program or application that allows communicators to interact with.

The definition of Youth

The word "teenager" is derived from the Latin is adolescent means to grow or to grow maturity. Many people who define youth, such as DeBrun (in Rice, 1990) defines adolescence as a period of growth between childhood to adulthood.

According to Papalia and Olds (2001), adolescence is a time of transition development between childhood and adulthood generally begins at age 12 or 13 years and ended at the age of late teens or early twenties years. Below among teenagers, they are familiar with terms such as e-mail, browsing, chatting, websites, blogs, and so on.

Findings

Data taken from the 368 parents who have teenage children who are studying in SMPK SANG TIMUR TANGERANG When teachers ask parents to choose

seminars are most needed for their child, from three options, namely sex education (14.9%), the dangers of drugs or drug abuse (17.8%) and the effect of the use of gadgets on the behavior of adolescents (67%). As many as 67% of parents choose seminar influence the use of gadgets on the behavior of adolescents assumes that the use of gadgets has entered the stage of worrying. The author surveyed how long teenagers use mobile phones here are the results:

1. A total of 35 students or 9.5% of students are not given cell phone but still be allowed to use belongs to the parents under the supervision of, typically loaned for use as a medium of learning when getting assignments from school, some are also allowed to play games but still in control of parents.
2. A total of 53 students or 14.4% given a private cell phone, but there is an agreement between the student and the parent. In one day be allowed to use 2-3 hours, exceptions holiday given more time.
3. A total of 56 students or 15.2% given a private cell phone, but there is an agreement between the student and the parent. In one day be allowed to use 1-1.5 hours, exceptions holiday given more time.

4. A total of 225 students, or 61% given a personal mobile phone and free use with no agreement.

According to parents, there are positive and negative effects on the use of cell phone

a. Positive impact

- As one source of information that can help the learning process. Internet providers of information and allow teens to get what is needed, which can support creativity. Even improve performance.
- As a means of communication that is the easiest and cheapest

b. Negative impact

- Being ignorant/selfish

Social media is media that can form a new world that is not real. Adolescents typically strive to actualize themselves here. When they are less acceptable in the real world, they will usually exist here, and when the virtual world is more attractive dam is considered to be more accepting of it is not uncommon teenagers become indifferent to the surrounding environment.

- Introvert

Adolescents and the virtual world is an inseparable unity. Not a

few teenagers have another image in the virtual world so they feel comfortable in it and do not want to forget the real-world disturbed by interference.

- Lazy to study

Using social media well it just to chat, watch movies, or play games certainly very exciting. If there is no control of parents and teachers as counselors, teenagers will not be the focus.

- No time management

Youth will take a long time on gadgets because of the information offered by the Internet indefinitely. All kinds of information about hobbies, entertainment or anything provided therein, do not be surprised if the young will forget to do things - other things.

- Games addiction

The recent news identifies the danger of playing games online without supervision be fatal even to death. It needs to be given limit, control or agreement must be agreed upon both parents and teens.

- Socialization in the real world are disturbed (stress)

Frequent misunderstandings occur virtual world. One can interpret anything he saw by the

way of thinking itself, because the visits are writing (no tone), then misunderstandings often occur. Not only was the writing that is updated on social media allows others to feel an update is addressed to him but not necessarily. Even *delcont* (delete contact) are things that can destroy friendships, *delcont* is a very big problem for teens to interact with friends.

- Inappropriate words

A teenager when very hungry for information, information available on the internet indefinitely, even information they do not need though. New vocabulary, even inappropriate slang language they will get. Not infrequently when they communicate by using language that is not appropriate, they do not realize that it was wrong, they think it's funny or cool, our task as educators and parents to instill positive value to them.

- Health issues

Sitting while playing a gadget without any physical movement can cause various health problems ranging from headaches to obesity. Staring at

the screen for too long a mobile phone will also endanger the health of the eye.

- Cost

Social media will be smoother if the quota is a great and good network. To get all the necessary costs. Costs to be incurred if it is too long to use the internet which is not necessary would have been a waste.

Effects of social media

Antisocial behavior experimental studies show that violent computer games as dangerous as the violence shown on television. Another study also found that video games have a greater ability to lead children to commit violence than violence on television and in real life. The Internet also brings pornography into the home and classroom. A recent survey showed that a quarter of children aged 10 to 17 years has been exposed to unwanted exposure to sexual material on the internet and some of them are very disappointed with the experience. Some of these unwanted exposure comes from various porn sites that try to make a lot of people visiting the site using the usual popular sites opened children. Another study about

interactive computer pornography found that there was no effect on the attitudes and aggressive acts against women among male college graduates. Computer anxiety Other studies focus more on the use of dysfunction that occurs on the computer itself, rather than the effect of its contents. Computer anxiety or what is commonly referred to as cyberphobia and computerphobia, the fears will be the computer itself. This phobia can result in nausea, vertigo, and cold sweat. Another fear for example fear of damaging if you press the wrong button, worry about the social effects of the computer, and fears on personal failure. This phobia suffered by women and people who have poor math skills. Other risks of computer addiction is an internet addict, which is motivated by the ability of computer media to interact and respond to the user's movement, either by doing what we want or not. It makes some people want to re-use it, cause addictive behavior. Evidence of this behavior is the collapse of the adults because too much time playing interactive games on the internet. This problem has spread to the tendency of doing gambling, such as fantasy sports leagues on the internet. The researchers suggest that the symptoms of internet addiction are an indication of the formation of habit media. A psychologist Sherry Turkle refers to the metaphor of persuasion, rather than dependency. The emphasis is holding

power on the computer does not come externally, but rather on its users.

Things that appear in social media

1) Impersonal

Each media led to differing degrees of reception substance messages in an interaction. The degree of acceptance is determined by the number of instructions nonverbal information available through the media. The theory behind this perspective is the Social Presence Theory (Short, Williams, and Christie, 1976). Social presence (social presence) is the degree to which we as individuals perceive others as private individuals and the interaction between them as a reciprocal relationship. Teens usually put through imaging so that they are perceived to exist by peers. When their status updates misconception is where the problem occurs frequently.

2) Interpersonal

Served as a marker of social context indicator of behavior socially unacceptable, which assumes that there are rules that control communicators, whether conscious or not direct the appropriate information is delivered and to whom the information is submitted or in communicating we adjust to our surroundings factor. This perspective refers to the innovative method of

conveying emotional content in their messages by using emoticons. There are four forms of emoticons that verbal form, a description of physical activity, stress or emphasis, and smiles.

3) Hyperpersonal

Hyperpersonal communication occurs when individuals find that they are better able to express themselves in social media rather than directly meet face to face.

CLOSING

Conclusion

Nowadays teenagers were born in the digital era amid the information society, the social media lives are part of teenager's life. Data were taken from the 368 parents who have teenage children who are studying in SMPK SANG TIMUR TANGERANG. When teachers ask parents to choose seminars that are most needed for their child, from three options, namely sex education (14.9%), the dangers of drugs or drugs abuse (17.8%) and the effect of the use of gadgets on the behavior of adolescents (67%). As many as 67% of parents choose a seminar about the influence the use of gadgets on the behavior of adolescents assume that the use of gadgets has entered the stage of worrying. The author surveyed how long teenagers use mobile phones here are the results:

1. A total of 35 students or 9.5% of students are not given cell phone but still be allowed to use belongs to the parents under the supervision of, typically loaned for use as a medium of learning when getting assignments from school, some are also allowed to play games but still in control of parents.
2. A total of 53 students or 14.4% given a private cell phone, but there is an agreement between the student and the parent. In one day be allowed to use 2-3 hours, exceptions holiday given more time.
3. A total of 56 students or 15.2% given a private cell phone, but there is an agreement between the student and the parent. In one day be allowed to use 1-1.5 hours, exceptions holiday given more time.
4. A total of 225 students, or 61% given a personal mobile phone and free use with no agreement.

According to parents, there are positive and negative effects on the use of this phone include

1. Positive impact
 - As one source of information that can help the learning process
 - As a means of communication that is the easiest and cheapest
2. Negative impact

- Being ignorant / selfish / closed
- Lazy to study
- Forgetting the time
- Games addict
- Inappropriate words
- Socialization in the real world are disturbed (stress)
- Health issues
- Cost

Suggestion

From the description above it can be concluded that it is necessary given the social media ethics education among young people, it is not only can be done by any school or old people. There needs to be a synergy between parents, schools and the environment. Thus, the authors suggest:

1. There needs social media ethics material included in one learning material in schools, for example through Character Building.
2. More parents take the time to monitor how teens communicate today and provide the value needed.
3. Today's teenagers were born in the digital age it is highly unlikely forbid them not to use social media, should at least be reproduced an appeal that carries a good message that contains about how to use healthy social media, attractively

packaged so that the message can be received by teens.

REFERENCES

Lon, Safko, (2010), *Social Media Bible Tactics, Tools, and Strategies For Business Succes*. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

Lister M, et al. (2009). *New Media : A Critical Introduction*. 2nd Edition. Routledge.

Galvin, Kathleen M & Bernard J, Brommel, (1986), *Family Communication: Cohesion and Change*, Scott, Foresman and Company, England.

Miller, Katherine, (2005). *Communication Theories: Perspectives, Processes, and Context*, International Edition, McGraw-Hill Inc, Asia

Segrin, Chris and Flora Jeanne, (2005) *Family Communication*, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, United States of America

Santrock, John W, (2003) *Adolescence, Perkembangan Remaja*. Jakarta, Erlangga
Zulkifli, (2005),

Psikologi Perkembangan, 2006, Bandung Remaja Rosdakarya,

Ihromi T.O, (2004), *Sosiologi Keluarga*, Jakarta Yayasan Obor Indonesia